

Publishable Summary for 23IND14 xDDiff

Multidimensional optical diffusion for the measurement of appearance

Overview

Product appearance and visual branding play important roles in influencing consumer purchase decisions, as they significantly shape perceptions of 'quality' and 'desirability'. However, solutions that enable industry to carry out reliable, stable and traceable measurements of the visual appearance of manufactured objects are still missing. This project aims to address that need by providing tools for carrying out the traceable measurement of the visual appearance of non-isotropic, non-flat and functional surfaces and of translucent materials. It will provide practical solutions for measuring haze, gloss, iridescence, matte and translucency of objects, which will also help to improve the quality of virtual reality rendering models.

Need

In industries dealing with real objects, product appearance and visual branding are important drivers for consumer purchase decisions because they underpin perceptions of 'quality' and 'desirability'. The control of appearance is thus essential for almost all traditional industrial fields (automotive, cosmetics, packaging, textile, paper). In industries involving virtual objects (videogames, metaverse, virtual prototyping, digital twins) and 3D printing, the quality of rendering and its realism are closely linked to the ability to capture and process the appearance of physical objects. This capability must match the performance level of the human visual system and align with the specific scale required for object's display or printing size. In advanced manufacturing industries, it is essential to have precise control over the directional reflectance and transmittance properties of materials to optimise reflection and/or transmission in specific parts of the optical spectrum. Additionally, this allows light to be redirected or guided in relevant directions to enhance the energy efficiency of buildings, greenhouses, light emitting diode (LED) lighting systems and photovoltaic panels.

Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function (BRDF) scales maintained by NMIs have been compared and consolidated over the past decade. However, the measurement of the BRDF at a few geometries is not enough to fully characterise the appearance of challenging surfaces and effects (e.g. brushed metals, functional surfaces, anisotropic samples and sparkle). For this, image-based goniospectrophotometers are required. They must be traceable and validated by comparison. Traceable BRDF measurements on non-flat surfaces have never been done even though the need has been expressed by industry for more than a decade. Bidirectional Transmittance Distribution Function (BTDF) and Bidirectional Surface Scattering Reflectance Distribution Function (BSSRDF) primary scales were established during EMPIR projects 18SIB03 BxDiff at the NMI level, but the uncertainty of BSSRDF measurements is still very high and must be reduced in order to answer the need of measurement of translucency.

Goniospectrophotometers developed at NMIs are very complex and their measurements very time consuming. To be used in industry, a simplification is required. For this, it is necessary to determine the relevant angular configurations, the sampling step and the sampling strategy according to the type of surface being studied. In colorimetry, there are metrics for comparing colour differences. However, no such metric exists for comparing BRDF measurements. Although progressing, the measurement of the BSSRDF is still not sufficient to simulate the appearance of translucency in rendering models. Moving forward requires the measurement of effective parameters such as scattering and absorption coefficients and the phase function of the material.

Report Status:
PU – Public, fully open

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METROLOGY PARTNERSHIP

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Whereas the measurement of gloss has progressed significantly over the last decade, the measurement of mattness is inexistent, even though this visual effect is very much used in industry. Therefore, it is crucial for work on the optical and visual characterisation of mattness to start. With regards to translucency, several psychophysical studies have been published in the last few years, but the link between BSSRDF and simplified quantities is still missing.

Objectives

The overall objective of the project is to provide industrial-level tools for capturing, reproducing and monitoring the visual appearance of real or virtual objects. The specific objectives of the project are:

1. To develop and characterise image-based goniospectrophotometers, including simplified versions of these and to use these to perform the traceable measurement of optical properties (e.g., BRDF, BTDF, BSSRDF) of actual manufactured surfaces e.g. anisotropic surfaces, non-flat surfaces, functional surfaces and translucent materials with a target measurement uncertainties below 0.5 % for BRDF and BTDF and around 2 % for BSSRDF for full goniospectrophotometers. The target uncertainties for simplified goniospectrophotometers are below 2 % for BRDF and BTDF and 4 % for BSSRDF.
2. To model complex scattering quantities (e.g., BRDF, BTDF, BSSRDF) of industrial surfaces to define quantifying tools for the digitalisation and reproduction of the appearance of materials, including thresholding, sampling strategy, interpolation models and comparison metrics.
3. To develop measurement scales for translucency and mattness. This includes the definition of physical quantities (e.g., BRDF and BSSRDF) which correlate with the visual sensation and the proposal of protocols for their measurement with a target uncertainty of 5 %.
4. To tackle metrological issues in the field of bidirectional spectrophotometry that limit the knowledge and the uncertainties on spectrophotometric quantities, i.e., sphere-based quantities, transmittance of thick samples, multiscale traceability, effective refractive index, specular gloss index.

To facilitate the take up of the technology and measurement infrastructure developed in the project by the EMN Advanced Manufacturing, measurement supply chain (NMIs, instrument manufacturers), standards developing organisations (ISO, CIE), and end users (e.g., automotive industry, video game developers, healthcare sector, visual arts sector, glass manufacturers).

Progress beyond the state of the art and results

This project follows on from previous projects EMRP project IND52 xDReflect, and EMPIR projects 16NRM08 BiRD, 18SIB03 BxDiff and 20SCP01 Smart PhoRa. The progress beyond the state of the art in relation to those projects is summarised below.

Objective 1: Development and characterisation of image-based goniospectrophotometers and their use in the traceable measurement of optical properties (e.g., BRDF, BTDF, BSSRDF) of actual manufactured surfaces

EMRP project IND52 [xDReflect](#) aimed at establishing primary references for BRDF dedicated to the measurement of appearance at the NMI level. Subsequently, EMPIR project 18SIB03 BxDiff successfully established primary references for BTDF and BSSRDF at the NMI level.

Although Europe has achieved the realisation of BRDF, BTDF and BSSRDF quantities that are traceable to the international system (SI) with the highest level of uncertainty, measuring these quantities at a limited number of geometries is insufficient to fully characterise the appearance of challenging industrial surfaces, such as brushed metals, functional surfaces and anisotropic samples. To address that issue, this project will go beyond the state of the art by developing traceable camera-based goniospectrophotometers at NMIs. This will bridge the gap between commercial devices and reference devices, reducing the calibration uncertainty.

Objective 2: Modelling of complex scattering quantities (e.g. BRDF, BTDF, BSSRDF) of industrial surfaces to define quantifying tools for the digitalisation and reproduction of the appearance of material

To improve our understanding of light-material interactions, simulate materials such as fabric or car paint in virtual prototyping, or manage the workflow of 3D printers, models of BRDF, BTDF and BSSRDF are required. While the field of computer graphics has produced numerous models over the past two decades, those are rarely validated against reliable measurements due to the absence of traceable measurements until now. This project aims to go beyond the state of the art by testing the most recent generation of BRDF/BTDF/BSSRDF

models against traceable measurements. This will enable the validation or reconsideration of long-standing assumptions related to parameters such as the “effective refractive index”, “phase function”, and “scattering and absorption coefficients”.

Objective 3: Development of measurement scales for translucency and mattness

Mattness and translucency are increasingly utilised in different industries e.g. automotive and ceramics. However, while the measurement of glossiness has made substantial progress over the last decade, the linkage between the perceptual qualities of mattness and translucency with BRDF and BSSRDF is still lacking. This project will go beyond the state of the art by developing numerical indicators extracted from BRDF and BSSRDF measurements. These indicators will quantitatively assess the levels of mattness and translucency in accordance with the visual perception of human observer.

Objective 4: Tackling of metrological issues in the field of bidirectional spectrophotometry

Currently, NMIs carry out BRDF measurements on one-square-centimetre surfaces, yet manufacturers often require measurements on much smaller surfaces. This project aims to advance beyond the existing state of the art by extending the traceability of BRDF measurements to sub-millimetre surfaces and making them accessible to industry.

Traditionally, the characterisation of transmittance haze and specular gloss relies on a relative methodology involving integrating spheres. However, direct access to these quantities through BRDF and BTDF measurements with goniospectrophotometers has become feasible. Nevertheless, recent findings suggest that the scales obtained through both methods do not agree as expected. The project intends to go beyond the state of the art by clarifying this discrepancy.

Outcomes and impact

Outcomes for industrial and other user communities

The project will deliver a new generation of goniospectrophotometers traceable to the SI and, in terms of optical design and measurement techniques, much closer to instruments used in industry to control or measure visual appearance. This will lead to reduced uncertainty in the calibration of measurement devices and enhanced control of the appearance of manufactured objects. For industry, this means: i) innovation and creation of new visual effects at the R&D stage, ii) less rejection/waste and improvement of the quality at the production level, and iii) reduction of conflict between suppliers and buyers at the delivery stage.

To promote the uptake of the project outputs by the industrial and other user communities, the consortium will organise workshops targeted at these communities and promote them online, at standardisation meetings and via the stakeholder committee.

Outcomes for the metrology and scientific communities

The development of these new goniospectrophotometers, their validation through intercomparisons, and the development of specific samples to support the quality of these comparisons will allow NMIs to validate their current, including recently developed, realisations of bidirectional spectrophotometric quantities.

Studies comparing measurements performed using integrating spheres with those obtained by integrating the BRDF or BTDF may have a significant impact. Presently, most NMIs rely on integrating spheres for their haze or gloss scales. If it turns out that measurement with goniospectrophotometers yield lower uncertainty, NMIs may consider modifying the traceability of haze and gloss measurements. This could extend to all primary measurements conducted using integrating spheres, including hemispherical reflectance or transmittance.

Finally, this project is committed to progress towards the establishment of a genuine European service for the metrology of appearance, which will include the new possibilities developed during the project for the measurement and characterisation of samples and visual effects.

To promote the uptake of the project outputs by the metrology and scientific communities, the consortium will organise workshops targeted at these communities and promote them online, at standardisation meetings and via the stakeholder committee.

Outcomes for relevant standards

The consortium has strong links with the CIE and will present the work and results of the project to CIE TC1-92, CIE TC2-85, CIE TC2-94, CIE TC2-98, CIE JTC 12 and CIE JTC 17. The consortium will actively strive to ensure incorporation of the outputs of the project into CIE Technical Recommendations, standards or guidelines. Additionally, the coordinating organisation is member of the BIPM CCPR and EURAMET-TC-PR, and the consortium has already established links with ISO/TC 6, SIS/TK 157, DfWG Deutsche farbwissenschaftliche Gesellschaft, DIN-Normenausschuss Farbe (FNF) and APMP-TC-PR.

Longer-term economic, social and environmental impacts

This project will make a significant contribution to improving the competitiveness of European industries by establishing a traceable system for measuring appearance, ensuring stability, interoperability, openness and objectivity.

This project aims to strengthen the competitiveness of the industry, potentially improving sales. While this goal may appear to conflict with the pressing need to reduce production and consumption for the preservation of our planet, improved control of appearance leads to better quality control, resulting in reduced waste. Additionally, enhanced rendering models promote more digital prototyping, potentially reducing the number of physical objects produced and distributed. The optimisation of sampling techniques results in reduced data generation and, consequently, decreased digital storage requirements.

Furthermore, the development of functional surfaces that can redirect or guide transmitted light in specific directions contributes to the enhanced energy efficiency of buildings, greenhouses, LED lighting systems, and photovoltaic panels. By enabling better characterisation of the reflective and transmissive properties of functional surfaces, the work carried out in this project will help to improve the performance of these surfaces and thus increase their efficiency.

The social impact of this project will be closely tied to the economic impact discussed above. Better control of appearance will lead to high customer satisfaction, and the improved capture of the appearance of objects will enable their digitalisation and the creation of digital twins of our cultural heritage so that they can be archived and ultimately preserved for future generations.

List of publications

This list is also available here: <https://www.euramet.org/repository/research-publications-repository-link/>

Project start date and duration:		01 June 2024
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